

TEXTUAL FEATURE ENGINEERING FOR CONCEPT CLASSIFICATION

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The following paper presents a framework to calculate a set of textual features to describe a *N-Grams* - a sequence of words. The different features take into account the *N-Grams* itself and the surrounding words. They belong either to the type of frequency-, probabilistic-, or similarity-based features. Different sets of features (contained in the shown framework) are used during the experiment to train models to extract *Concepts* from the text. The performance of those models is measured in four different text collections and compared with another Neural Network based approach. Secondly, the evaluation uses the trained models inside a pipeline to identify the essential phrase inside a text. The second stage of the evaluation uses three other methods to compare performance.

Index Terms— Natural Language Processing, Information Retrieval, Concept Extraction, Keyphrase Extraction, Feature Extraction, Feature Selection

I. INTRODUCTION

Algorithm and methods in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) use textual resources to extract information or identify similarities. Those approaches (such as [1]) use Bag of Word (BoW) as features for further processing. Representing a text with a BOW represents the text as a set of the existing words and their frequency. Thus, a lot of context information is lost. Bag of N-Gram (BoN) instead can cover more contextual information by storing the frequency of word combinations. As shown by [2], the extraction of the underlying sentiment of a text can gain better performance by using BoN. Also, the approach - introduced in [3] - can profit of the usage BoN for text classification.

The research project Cross-Platform Mediation, Association and Search Engine (XMAS) extracts *Concepts* from unstructured data to create new knowledge structures. We showed in [4] a method of extracting *Keyphrases* from a document. This extraction assembles a subset of the BoN by preserving the more informative

N-Grams (Concepts) and filter out the less informative (*Non-Concepts*). This subset is called the Bag of Concepts (BoC) as used in [5] or [6]. The set of *Keyphrases* consists of the most informative *Concepts* of such a BoC. This restriction use a mixture of statistical information from the document and the corpus.

We used in [4] a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to distinguish between a *Concept* and a *Non-Concept* in order to build the BoC. The usage of word embeddings in this approach makes it harder to understand how a prediction is composed. The understanding of those decision processes is nearly as important as the performance. Even more, since the human judgment of a reasonable *Concept* changes from person to person, and is affected by latent aspects. This paper aims to overcome those issues by addressing the following research questions are:

- i What are meaningful and understandable features for text classification, such as *Concept Extraction*?
- ii How can those features be ordered and selected?
- iii How is it possible to represent an *N-Gram* with a dynamic number of words with features of fixed dimensions?
- iv Is it possible to encode the context of the *N-Gram* in the set of features?
- v How well performs *Concept Extraction* models (based on the formulated features) in contrast the previous approach (CNN), and how do they affect the performance of the *Keyphrase Extraction*?
- vi Is there a way for a better understanding of the ongoing decision processes of those models in comparison to the previous approach with CNN?

The reasoning about this research question is organized into five parts. First, the introduction of the related work(section II) and secondly proposed methods to solve those questions (section III). Then the section IV shows the structure of the evaluation of the proposed method. The section V consists of the results measured during the experiment in combination with an example of interpreting ongoing decision processes. In the end, the section VI, section VII, and section VIII

interprets the observed results, answer the research question, summarize the most essential aspects, and gives a short outlook. Some of the large tables can be found in the appendix (section A).

II. RELATED WORK

The following section gives an overview of the related work and important topics such as possible text features, feature selection, and model interpretability.

II-A. Automated Concept Extraction

The dimensionality of a Bag of N -Gram is approximate n times bigger than a Bag of Word. The automated extraction of *Concepts* tries to lower this dimensionality by classifying N -Grams as *Concepts* or *Non-Concepts*. *Concepts*, as defined by [7], are word combinations with a higher amount of contained information than any other random selected Non-Concept. As a rule of thumb, *Concepts* all having a Wikipedia entry. Taking into account the following sentence with 178 N -Grams (up to 7 words). The N -Gram *Republic of Ecuador* gives much more information about the text than a noisy N -Gram like *on either side of*.

The Galápagos Islands, part of the Republic of Ecuador, are an archipelago of volcanic islands distributed on either side of the equator in the Pacific Ocean surrounding the center of the Western Hemisphere.¹

The enclosing noise of a BoN is calculated as the percentage of *Non-Concepts* of all N -Grams. The amount of noise increase with a higher number of words inside of a N -Grams. The Table II backs this intuition by showing the *Concepts* and percentage of *Non-Concepts* for all N -Grams with one to seven words of the previous text sample.

Other approaches for the extraction process beside Neural Networks and Word Embeddings are semantic approaches like considering word connections ([8]) or a combination of statistic and linguistic methods, as in [7].

II-B. Text Features

During the phase of preprocessing and feature extraction, numeric metrics are calculated for words, N -Grams, or even whole documents. Those numeric representations can be used afterward as an input of further applications. [9] introduces amongst other metrics the following ones:

- Term Frequency $tf_{w,d}$ - also known as Bag-of-Words model - represents the number of occurrences of a word w inside of a document d . To

¹available on [Wikipedia](#)

	Members of a BoC	% of Non-Concepts
<i>Uni-Gram</i>	Galápagos, Islands, Republic, Ecuador, archipelago, volcanic, islands, equator, Pacific, Ocean, Western, Hemisphere	64 %
<i>Bi-Gram</i>	Galápagos Islands, volcanic islands, Pacific Ocean, Western Hemisphere	88 %
<i>Tri-Gram</i>	Republic of Ecuador	96 %
<i>Tetra-Gram</i>	archipelago of volcanic islands	96 %
<i>Penta-Gram</i>	centre of the Western Hemisphere	96 %
<i>Hexa-Gram</i>	-	100 %
<i>Hepta-Gram</i>	-	100 %

Table II. Assumed *Concepts*

gather this information the position inside the text is ignored and all words are equally important.

- Collection Frequency $cf_{w,c}$ - like the tf it counts the occurrence of a word w but inside all documents of a collection c and not just in one document.
- Document Frequency df_w - in contrary to the tf and cf the df count the number of documents containing a certain word w .
- Inverse Document Frequency idf_w - to reduce the weight of high frequently and useless words, such as stopwords. The idf metric gives a high weight to rare words. As shown in Equation 1 the idf value is the logarithm of the total number of documents N divided by the df .

$$idf_w = \log\left(\frac{N}{df_w}\right) \quad (1)$$

- Since the tf gives a high weight to highly frequent words inside one document and the idf increase the weight of rare words. Those two combined ($tfidf_{w,d} = tf_{w,d} * idf_w$) prefers rare words which appears a lot in the given document.
- Pointwise Mutual Information $pmi_{a,b}$ - is used to describe the amount of dependence of the event a and the event b (shown in Equation 2).

$$pmi_{a,b} = \log\left(\frac{P(a,b)}{P(a) * P(b)}\right) \quad (2)$$

There are other used metrics described in the literature:

- Residual Inverse Document Frequency $ridf_{p,d}$ - as described in [10] is the difference of the real idf and expected value by using a Poisson distribution with lambda equal to the average tf of a N -Gram p (Equation 3, Equation 4).

$$\theta = \frac{cf_{p,c}}{N} \quad (3)$$

$$ridf_{p,d} = idf_{p,d} - \log\left(\frac{1}{(1 - e^\theta)}\right) \quad (4)$$

- Maximum Spread Distance $msd_{p,d}$ - shown in [11] is the difference between the index of first occurrence of a N -Gram p and the last occurrence inside a document d .

II-C. Language Model

Based on the Markov Chain Rule the probability for a N -Gram containing the words w_1, \dots, w_n can be expressed as shown in Equation 5.

$$P(w_1, \dots, w_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(w_i | w_{i-1}, \dots, w_1) \quad (5)$$

With a growing vocabulary, calculating those probabilities are getting hard and expensive. *Language Models* can help to simplify and speed up those calculations. As described in [9], a *Probabilistic Model* exists as soon a probability distribution gives us the probability of any next state based on the current state. Such a state can be any word, punctuation marks, the sentence beginning, or the sentence closing. A *1-Gram Model* w_1, \dots, w_n can be expressed $P(w_1, \dots, w_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(w_i)$. Using *2-Gram Model* w_1, \dots, w_n includes also information about the surround words. It can be expressed as $P(w_1, \dots, w_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(w_i | w_{i-1})$.

II-D. Feature Selection

Feature selection, as in [12], helps to understand the data, reduce the training time, and combat the curse of dimensionality to improve the predictive power. The selection process ranks the features according to internal or external measurement. The internal ones calculate the importance of every feature f_a with respect of the target variable y . Depending on the type of the target variable, the importance can be calculated differently:

- If the target is a dichotomous variable the point-biserial correlation (introduced by [13]) can be used as stated in Equation 6. It uses f_a^+ and f_a^- as set of samples belonging to one of target values (+ or -). Furthermore μ^+ , μ^- as the mean value of f_a within the samples set f_a^+ and f_a^- , p^+ and p^- as the probability of observing a sample in one of the two sample set and $f_{a\sigma}$ as the standard deviation of the feature f_a within all samples.
- In the case of a categorical target variable, the one-way ANOVA test can be used. It starts from the null hypothesis that the combination of the feature value f_a and the target y just occurred by chance. Since the p-value represents the acceptance probability of the null hypothesis, the inverse $(1 - p)$ can be used as a measure of the importance of f_a .

- As a third option, the target could be numerical in case of a regression task. For this purpose, the Pearson correlation can be used, as shown in Equation 7.

$$biserial = \frac{\mu^+ - \mu^-}{f_{a\sigma}} * \sqrt{p^+ * p^-} \quad (6)$$

$$r = \frac{n \sum_{i=0}^n f_{a_i} f_{b_i} - \sum_{i=0}^n f_{a_i} \sum_{i=0}^n f_{b_i}}{\sqrt{n \sum_{i=0}^n f_{a_i}^2 - (\sum_{i=0}^n f_{a_i})^2} \sqrt{n \sum_{i=0}^n f_{b_i}^2 - (\sum_{i=0}^n f_{b_i})^2}} \quad (7)$$

External measurements - as in [14] - uses tree based model to calculate a feature importance. Those models use all the possible features as input and the target y as training signal. After the training, the feature importance of the model is used to rank the features.

II-E. Model Interpretation

Neural Network or complex Ensemble Models getting much attention over the past few years in various fields. With the growing complexity of those models, the interpretability why and how a model makes a decision decreases. There are different methods to solve those issues and try to make complex models better explainable in a simple way. The consideration of a global or local point of view can help to make a model more explainable. One global approach (purposed by [15]) calculates the importance of the features by considering the model a black box. Another global measurement is the Partial Dependence of one or more features ([16]). It is the idea of measure the change of the prediction when changing one or more features while keeping the other constant. In contrast to global, local measurements use single examples to deviate a certain prediction. One method is stated by [17] and can explain how the prediction is made with regards to every single feature and the corresponding value.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

The following section describes the proposed approach to define text features, a way of calculating them, and how to produce limited sets of those features. The following theoretical description focus on the generic structure of this approach. The section IV shows in contrast to this section, the application with specific datasets and how the generated features can be used for building a *Concept Extraction* model.

III-A. Textual Feature Framework

Figure 1 shows the the seven steps of the *Textual Feature Framework*. They calculate and weight the features with two datasets (*Preparation* and *Calculation*

Dataset) and a Golden Standard. The Preparation Dataset is a large set of text to as a approximation of the general language structure and the Calculation Dataset is another set of texts to reduce the bias comping from the Preparation Dataset. First of all the Data Preparation step does the preprocessing of those datasets. Afterward, the First Level Feature Calculation extracts the frequencies and co-occurrence of all the different words. The Second Level Feature Calculation use those information to calculate the necessary statistical and probabilistic information. In the fourth step, the Third Level Feature Calculation uses the previously gained information to compute the textual features for the samples in the preprocessed (step three) Calculation Dataset. The fifth step scales the computed features to a common scale before the different features are weighted during the sixth step. This feature weighting uses the target label for each sample, which is coming from the third required dataset (Golden Standard). The seventh step removes the redundant features inside the weighted lists of features. In the end, the Feature Weights Store contains all sorted cleaned list of features and the Calculation Store the results of the First and Second Level Feature Calculation to calculate features for unseen samples. Those results can then be used, for example, to train a Concept Extraction model.

Fig. 1. Textual Feature Framework

III-B. Feature Structure

Before looking into the different steps of the calculation, the following paragraph states the basic structure of one sample and how the different feature groups and categories describe it. The Figure 2 shows the basic structure of one sample with the *N-Gram* in the middle and the neighbor words on the left and on the right. A window controls the number of neighbors words to

consider. The length of this window can be flexible due to the dynamic formulation of the features. However, at the moment, it is fixed to one due to the higher computational costs.

Fig. 2. Feature Structure

Based on this structure, the features of a samples belongs to one of the following category of features, *N-Gram-* (N), *Surrounding-* (S) and *Transition-Features* (T). The *N-Gram-* and *Surrounding-Features* characterize the *N-Gram* itself and the surrounding words $word_{start-1}, word_{end+1}$. And the *Transition-Features* hold the information about the transition into and out of the *N-Gram* captured by two pairs of border words. Either the word on the left ($word_{start-1}$) and the first word ($word_{start}$) of the *N-Gram* or the word on the right ($word_{end+1}$) and the last word (w_{end}) of the *N-Gram*. Besides those categories, each feature belongs to one of the following groups, frequency-based, probabilistic based, or similarity-based features.

III-C. Data Preparation

The phase of *Data Preparation* preprocesses all the texts in the *Preparation Dataset* and *Calculation Dataset* for the next steps. This is done by clean those up and add special tokens:

- Lower all the text.
- Remove all the carriage return and line feed characters.
- Split text into sentences.
- Surround each sentence $\langle ST \rangle$ (sentence starts) and $\langle SE \rangle$ (sentence ends).
- Replace brackets, curved brackets and quotes and double quotes with $\langle PS \rangle$ (phrase starts) or $\langle PE \rangle$ (phrase ends).
- Replace comma with $\langle CO \rangle$
- Stem all words of the documents by an implementation of the algorithm proposed by [18].
- Create all the sample according to the previous shown feature structure.

III-D. First Level Feature Calculation

The first phase of the feature precalculation creates the language model. This computation uses all pre-processed texts of the *Preparation Dataset* corpus and consists of the following four matrices:

- The priori-matrix $PR(m,m)$ contains the occurrence c_{ij} of a stem s_i before a stem s_j . The reversed version of this matrix is the posteriori-matrix $PO(m,m)$. It contains the occurrence c_{ij} of a stem s_i after s_j . Those matrices enables the calculation of all probabilistic based features.
- The term frequency matrix $TF(m,n)$ contains the information about the appearance of the stems s_1, \dots, s_m inside all the documents d_1, \dots, d_n of the corpus. This information can be used to calculate frequency-based features.
- In the end a fourth matrix $NSD(m,n)$ is calculated containing the normalized spread distance of all stems s_1, \dots, s_m in each document d_1, \dots, d_n . The Equation 8 defines the normalized spread distance for a stem s in a document d .

$$f(s,d) = \frac{\text{index}_n(s,d) - \text{index}_0(s,d)}{\text{length}_d} \quad (8)$$

III-E. Second Level Feature Calculation

In a second step of the calculation, the base matrices are used to calculate the following data structures:

- The vector \vec{df} contains the document frequency (Equation 9) for each stem s based on the TF matrix.

$$f(s) = \sum_{i=0}^n \begin{cases} 1, & 0 < TF_{s,d_i} \\ 0, & \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

- For each of the stem s , the vector $\vec{tf}_\mu, \vec{tf}_\sigma$ contains the mean and standard deviation for the three base matrices TF, PO, PR as show in Equation 10 to Equation 15.

$$f(s) = \frac{1}{n} * \sum_{i=0}^n TF_{s,d_i} \quad (10)$$

$$f(s) = \frac{1}{n} * \sum_{i=0}^n PR_{s,d_i} \quad (11)$$

$$f(s) = \frac{1}{n} * \sum_{i=0}^n PO_{s,d_i} \quad (12)$$

$$f(s) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n (TF_{s,d_n} - tf_{\mu_s})^2} \quad (13)$$

$$f(s) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n (PR_{s,d_n} - pr_{\mu_s})^2} \quad (14)$$

$$f(s) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n (PO_{s,d_n} - po_{\mu_s})^2} \quad (15)$$

- The inverse document frequencies and residual inverse document frequencies are stored inside the

two vectors \vec{idf} and \vec{ridf} for all s . The calculation follows the Equation 16 and Equation 17.

$$\vec{idf} = \log\left(\frac{n}{df}\right) \quad (16)$$

$$f(s) = idf_s - \log\left(\frac{1}{(1 - e^{ts})}\right) \quad (17)$$

- Afterwards the previous calculations enables the calculation of the two new matrices $TFIDF$ and $TFRIDF$. Equation 18) and Equation 19 show how they are calculated with the Hadamard product.

$$TFIDF(m,n) = TF \circ \begin{pmatrix} idf^T \\ \vdots \\ idf^T \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$TFRIDF(m,n) = TF \circ \begin{pmatrix} ridf^T \\ \vdots \\ ridf^T \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

- In a next step the mean and standard deviation vectors $\vec{tfidf}_\mu, \vec{tfidf}_\sigma, \vec{tfridf}_\mu, \vec{tfridf}_\sigma$ of the matrices $TFIDF$ and $TFRIDF$ is done as shown in Equation 20, Equation 22, Equation 21 and Equation 23 for all stems s .

$$f(s) = \frac{1}{n} * \sum_{i=0}^n TFIDF_{s,d_i} \quad (20)$$

$$f(s) = \frac{1}{n} * \sum_{i=0}^n TFRIDF_{s,d_i} \quad (21)$$

$$f(s) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n (TFIDF_{s,d_n} - tfidf_{\mu_s})^2} \quad (22)$$

$$f(s) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n (TFRIDF_{s,d_n} - tfridf_{\mu_s})^2} \quad (23)$$

- The three matrices $TFIDF, TFRIDF$ and PR are used to express similarity-based features. All of those are high dimensional sparse matrices. The high dimensionality leads to computationally expensive similarity calculations, which suffer from the curse of dimensionality. The reduction of those matrices to 200 dimensions tries to overcome those limitations. This reduction is made by applying Truncated SVD as presented by [19]. In contrast to PCA, it can also handle sparse matrices since it does not need to calculate the covariance matrix. The construction of reduced matrices $TFIDF_{SVD}, TFRIDF_{SVD}$ and PR_{SVD} follows the Equation 24 for matrix X :

$$X \approx X_{SVD} = U_{200} * \Sigma_{200} * V_{200}^T \quad (24)$$

III-F. Third Level Feature Calculation

This step takes care of calculations the final features for all the samples of the preprocessed *Calculation Dataset*. The *N-Gram* of the samples can contain up to seven stems, as shown in subsection III-B. To get a fixed representation of this dynamic number of stems, the mean μ and standard deviation σ of those is calculated. Assumed that those values are approximated Gaussian distributed. The way of calculating this statistic depends on the specific kind of feature and follows one of the following three possibilities:

- 1) Each stem s of a sample has a specific value such as idf_s . The set of those values is used to calculate the statistic of the values (μ and σ).
- 2) Each stem s of the sample is represented as a statistic (σ and μ) based on a set of values. For example, the different term frequencies of s in all documents d_1, \dots, d_n of the corpus. This set of statistics is used to calculate the compound statistic. It contains the statistic of the set of standard deviations ($\sigma_\sigma, \mu_\sigma$) and the statistic of the set of means σ_μ, μ_μ .
- 3) Every stem pair s_1, s_2 of a *N-Gram* is used to calculate a value such as the conditional probability $P(s_2|s_1)$. Either based on a sequence of appearance in the *N-Gram* $(s_1, s_2), (s_2, s_3), \dots, (s_{n-1}, s_n)$ or the combination of all possible pairs of stems regardless of the order $(s_1, s_2), (s_1, s_3), \dots, (s_{n-1}, s_n)$. Afterward, a statistic (σ, μ) of those values is calculate to represent them.

The tables in subsection A shows the formulation of the final features by using the precalculations of the previous two steps. The corresponding calculation for the different feature groups are formulated in Table X for the frequency-based features, Table XI for the probabilistic-based features, and Table XII for the similarity-based features. The similarity-based features using either the cosine (Equation 25) or Euclidean (Equation 26) similarity.

$$\cos(\vec{A}, \vec{B}) = \frac{\vec{A} * \vec{B}}{\|\vec{A}*\|_2 \|\vec{B}\|_2} \quad (25)$$

$$euc(\vec{A}, \vec{B}) = \|\vec{A} - \vec{B}\|_2 \quad (26)$$

III-G. Feature Standardization

The z-score normalization (as shown in Equation 27) scale all the features to a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1. This scaling is done by subtracting the mean value of the feature μ_{f_a} from the original value f_a , divided with the standard deviation of the feature σ_{f_a} . Furthermore, this process makes the features better comparable and optimizes the features for the usage in

different kind of models such as k-nearest neighbors or Logistic Regression.

$$\hat{f}_a = \frac{f_a - \mu_{f_a}}{\sigma_{f_a}} \quad (27)$$

III-H. Feature Weighting

The measurement of the weight of all features is used to sort these. This sorted list is the base of creating a limited set of the best features. There are different internal and external measurements which cover various aspects of the features. Such elements can be single feature groups (such as *transition* features) or a subset of the samples (for example just *bigrams*). All of those measurements use the target variable y (coming from the *Golden Standard*) to calculate the weights. The internal measurements use either the point-biserial correlation for dichotomous variables, the one-way ANOVA test for a categorical variable, or the Pearson correlation (Equation 7) for numeric one. The external measurement, use all the features to train a *Decision Tree* and a *Random Forest* classifier. Both classifiers were trained on predicting the target y by using 20-fold cross-validation. Afterward, the feature importance of both models is used to weight all the features.

III-I. Feature Cleaning

The different sorted lists of features contain potential redundant features. These redundancies can reduce the performance of the final model. A pair of features f_a, f_b is redundant if the Pearson correlation of them is higher than 0.9. This threshold is fixed due to computational calculations of the whole process, and it can be a hyperparameter for potential improvements. The algorithm 1 shows how redundant features are removed. It loops through one of the previously sorted lists of features. For each feature f in this list, it goes through the list of already cleaned features in an inner loop. This list of neat features is empty in the beginning. In one iteration of the inner loop, the correlation of actual feature f and the actual clean feature f_c is calculated as shown in Equation 7. If this correlation is not more significant than 0.9, f is added to the list of neat features otherwise, f is skipped.

IV. DESIGN OF EXPERIMENT

After the theoretical discourse of the *Textual Feature Framework* this section focus on how to build it, the usage of the resulting feature sets, and finally the structure of the evaluation. For this purpose, the different datasets - shown in the following section subsection IV-A - are used to build the framework

Input: ordered list of features

Output: ordered list of cleaned features

```
foreach  $f \in features$  do
   $i \leftarrow 0$ 
  foreach  $f_c \in features_{clean}$  do
    if  $|correlation(f, f_c)| > 0.9$  then
       $i += 1$ 
    end
  if  $i = 0$  then
     $features_{clean} += f$ 
  end
end
```

Algorithm 1: Feature cleaning

and calculate, rank the formulated features, and compose them into different feature sets. Afterward, the training of the *Concept Extraction* models use the different variations of feature sets. The performance of those models is measured three times. Once with the results of the training (subsection IV-C) to measure the stability of the models. Once on during the testing phase (subsection IV-D) to measure the performance on the *Concept Extraction* on the test set. And once on *Keyphrase Extraction* (subsection IV-E) to measure the change of the performance of the *Keyphrase Extraction* ([4]) by using the trained models. Overall the precision, recall, and f1 score are used as a measurement of the performance.

IV-A. Used Datasets

The different phases of the experiment use the following datasets. The purpose of those datasets inside the framework is explained later on in the following sections.

- *Wikipedia Dataset*, a collection of almost 5.5 million english Wikipedia articles.
- *Wikipedia Titles*, all the titles of *Wikipedia Dataset*. They are filtered as proposed by [7] in order to enhance the quality by removing unwanted entries like verbs or pronouns.
- *News Store*, a dataset of 150'000 news articles from various publishing networks.²
- *Training Dataset*, a portion of 20% of all *N-Grams* of 20% of the *News Store* to get topically even distributed samples. This set comprise around 5 million *N-Grams* together with their predecessor and processor word. They are not even distributed with regards to the length of their *N-Gram*, and to the ratio of *Concepts* and *Non-Concepts* within the samples with the same *N-Gram* length. Especially for higher *N-Gram* length, the proportion of *Concepts* goes down to around 0.1 %.

²available on [Kaggle](#)

- *DUC Dataset*, it contains the 308 test documents of the DUC2001 corpus. This corpus is built of news article with manually annotated *Keyphrases*.³
- *Hulth Dataset*, it contains of the 500 test documents of the Hulth corpus. All of those documents are abstracts of journal articles, manually annotated with *Keyphrases*. [20]

IV-B. Preparation

In the preparation phase of the experiment the *Textual Feature Framework* is built by using the *Wikipedia Dataset* as *Preparation Dataset*, the *Training Dataset* as *Calculation Dataset*, and the *Wikipedia Titles* as *Golden Standard* according to Figure 1. They are used to do the precalculations as in subsection III-D, subsection III-E, and compute the formulated features, shown in subsection III-F, for all the samples in the *Training Dataset*. The precalculations are stored in the *Calculation Store* for later calculation of the features for new samples.

As a next step, the *Feature Weighting* (subsection III-H) use those samples together with the corresponding label from the *Wikipedia Titles* to calculate the goodness of the different features. The internal measurement of this goodness is calculated as the point-biserial correlation with the target. Different variations of this internal measurement capture different aspects and gain to overcome the imbalance with regards to the *N-Gram* length. The following list shows those five basic variations:

- *total_n*, correlation of every single feature with the target and the absolute values-based.
- *mean*, mean of the seven correlation values of the grouped samples by the number of words (one to seven).
- *total_2*, Correlation of every single features with the target, by just considering the *Bi-grams* samples.
- *total_3*, Correlation of every single features with the target, by just considering the *Tri-grams* samples.
- *total_4*, Correlation of every single features with the target, by just considering the *Tetra-grams* samples.

Based on the five basic variations, additional variations are composed by permuting the following aspects:

- Basic variations, *total_n*, *mean*, *total_2*, *total_3*, *total_4*
- Using all samples or a *balanced* set of samples regarding to the target.

³available on [nist](#)

- Considering all the features, just those of the category *Transition* or the category *N-Gram* (introduced in subsection III-B).

Finally, the following four external measurements are added to the internal ones:

- *dec_tree_max dec_tree_mean*, Feature importance calculated by a decision tree. Once the max value of the 20 times cross-validation and once the mean value per feature.
- *rand_forest_max rand_forest_mean*, Feature importance calculated by a random forest. Once the max value of the 20 times cross-validation and once the mean value per feature.

Now, the *Textual Feature Framework* produce a sorted list of features based on the corresponding feature weights for each of the measurement. In the last step of building the feature sets, the redundant features are removed by using the procedure seen in subsection III-I. Those cleaned sets are stored afterward in the *Feature Weights Store* for the actual training process.

IV-C. Training and Validation

The phase of Training and Validation trains the different models with the features sets. The *Calculation Store* holds all the necessary precalculations, the *Feature Weights Store* contains the 64 sorted feature lists, and the *Training Dataset* the necessary samples. Those samples are labeled with the *Wikipedia Titles*. The training consists 2'300 different models. Each of the trained models is a permutation of the following hyperparameters:

- *Feature Weights*, the 64 list of sorted features.
- *Number of Feature*, the number of top features based on the sort list of feature weights, either 10, 20 or 30 features.
- *Number of Samples*, the number of samples to train the model on out of the 5 million samples available. Due to the large amount memory needed during the training process, this is limited to 1, 2 or 3 million.
- *Model Type*, the last hyper parameter is the type of the model. Table IV show the four possibilities and their parameters. All of those are used out of the box provided by [21]:

The training of each model starts with generating a feature set based on the corresponding hyperparameters. This feature is fed forward into a training set and a validation set. The 20-fold cross-validation trains every model on a unique proportion of the training set - containing 95% of the samples. Afterward, for every run of the cross-validation, the performance is calculated on the 5% leftover samples of the training set. All of those runs are used to calculate the mean

Model Type	Parameters
<i>Multinomial Naïve Bayes</i>	Default
<i>Logistic Regression</i>	Default
<i>Decision Tree</i>	Minimum number of samples to split a internal node equals to 40
<i>Random Forest</i>	Minimum number of samples to split an internal node equals to 40 and number of trees equals to 50

Table IV. Different Model Type and their parameters

and standard deviation of the performance metrics. In the last step, the final model is trained on the whole training set, and saved in the *Model Store* together with the list of used features. Afterward, the calculation of the validation performance uses the validation set to calculate the metrics.

IV-D. Concept Extraction Evaluation

The evaluation of *Concept Extraction* measures the performance of the built model on the test set. The test set consists of the following four different data set to get a generalized performance.

- 1) *Hulth Dataset*
- 2) *DUC Dataset*
- 3) 1'000 random selected documents of the *Wikipedia Store*
- 4) 1'000 articles of *News Store* which are not used for the *Training Store*

The calculation of the performance metrics use the *Wikipedia Titles* again as reference.

IV-E. Keyphrase Extraction Evaluation

The integrated evaluation in the *Keyphrase Extraction* use the trained models as a part of the whole pipeline. We presented (in [4]) this pipeline as a way of extraction *Keyphrases* stepwise used in the *XMAS* project. In the pipeline, the *Concept Extraction* filters the potential *Keyphrase* candidates. Afterward, the set of candidates are weighted by a combination of different statistical measurements. The calculated weight is then used to order the candidates and select the top *k* candidates as *Kexphrases*. This evaluation uses the *DUC* and *Hulth Dataset*. Both of them coming with manually annotated *Keyphrase*. The calculation of the performance metrics uses this manual annotation as a reference to the truth.

V. RESULTS

The next section describes the results of the training phase (subsection V-A), of the testing phase (subsection V-B), and the *Keyphrase Extraction* (subsection V-C). The results contains a detailed plot for each of this three evaluation. It shows the performance metrics

with regards to the feature group (subsection III-B), number of features, number of samples, model type, and feature measurement (subsection IV-B). Additional the subsection V-D shows how to understand the resulting models and subsection V-E the understanding of the ongoing decision process based on the seen methods in subsection II-E.

V-A. Stability

Stability represents the generalization of a model. It is measured as the standard deviation of the precision of the 20 cross-validation runs per model. The lower the value, the better the stability. All the models have an average std. precision of 2.4%. Figure 3 shows more details, including the std. deviation and the mean f1 score (cross-validated f1) of all the cross-validation runs:

- *Decision Tree* models have a std. precision of 0.59%, the *Random Forest* models 0.68%, and the other two models type a score of 4.6% (*Logistic Regression*) and 3.8% (*Naive Bayes*). Overall *Random Forest* and *Decision Tree* the higher cross-validated f1 score.
- The stability changes with regards to the different feature measurement. The *dec_tree_mean* has the best stability with a score of 0.35%, while the others have a score of about 1.4% to 3.3%. In general, the four external feature measurements have the higher cross-validated f1 score then the five internal ones.
- The use of more features makes *Naive Bayes* and *Logistic Regression* models less stable while adding more samples supports the stability.
- Models with *full* features have a stability of 1.1% while the other twos (*ngram* and *transition*) have scores of 2.9% and 3.3%.
- The stability has a Pearson correlation of -0.533 with the f1 score.
- In terms of time complexity *Naive Bayes* models are built with a mean time of 5 seconds, the *Logistic Regression* and *Decision Tree* models with 223 seconds, and the *Random Forest* with 972 seconds.

V-B. Concept Extraction Evaluation

This evaluation consists of a general overview of all trained models, an detailed performance plot, and a comparison of selected models with the previous approach (CNN). The performance is measured as precision, recall, f1 score, and mean length.

The trained models cover a wide performance range from low to high scores (shown in Figure 4). The *Decision Tree* models have an almost linear relationship between precision and recall. The *Random Forest* models strengthen the precision, and the other twos favor, in

Fig. 3. Training performance

general, a larger recall score. Additional, one single model has an average deviation of the mean length of 0.09, of the precision of 0.03, and the recall 0.02 on the four different test sets.

Fig. 4. Scatter plot of precision and recall of all models

Figure 5 shows more details of the average performance on the four test sets:

- The *Decision Tree* models have a f1 score 0.53 and a mean length of 1.83. *Random Forest* models a f1 score of 0.49 and a mean length of 1.46. Additional the *Logistic Regression* and *Naive Bayes* models have mean length 1.86 and a f1 score of 0.35, and 0.21.
- The external feature measurements (*dec_tree_mean*, *dec_tree_max*, *rand_forest_mean*, *rand_forest_max*) have a f1 score between 0.53 to

0.56 and a mean length of 1.19 to 1.44 in contrast to the internal measurements with a mean f1 score of 0.33 to 0.41 and mean length of 1.74 to 1.84.

- The models with the *transition* features have f1 score 0.09 compared to the other twos with 0.52 (*full*) and 0.56 (*ngram*).
- The number of features do not have a big impact on the mean length and stability except of the *Naive Bayes* models. They have a lower mean length and f1 score when the number of features increase.
- The Pearson correlation between the mean f1 score and the mean length is -0.61.

Fig. 5. Concept Extraction/Testing Performance

Table V shows the comparison of models trained with the *Textual Features* and the CNN models. This comparison includes for the precision, recall, and f1 the model with the highest, the lowest, and the median score. The table contains the complete feature set (precision *pr*, recall *re*, f1 score *f1*, mean length *avg*) of the single selected models. Overall the models trained with the *Textual Features* have a higher precision and f1 score than the CNN models while the CNN models achieve a lot better recall scores.

V-C. Keyphrase Extraction Evaluation

This evaluation step measures the impact of using one the trained model inside the *Keyphrase Extraction* pipeline. Figure 6 shows the measured mean performance on the *DUC* and *Hulth* Dataset:

Metric	Textual Features				CNN				
	<i>pr</i>	<i>re</i>	<i>f1</i>	<i>avg</i>	<i>pr</i>	<i>re</i>	<i>f1</i>	<i>avg</i>	
precision	median	0.60	0.61	0.60	1.11	0.28	0.99	0.45	1.46
	min	0.10	0.16	0.12	3.38	0.24	0.99	0.39	1.60
	max	0.80	0.92	0.86	1.1	0.33	0.94	0.48	1.28
recall	median	0.70	0.71	0.70	1.22	0.26	0.98	0.41	1.49
	min	0.32	0.10	0.15	2.15	0.32	0.94	0.47	1.46
	max	0.13	0.99	0.22	2.61	0.26	0.99	0.40	1.33
f1	median	0.59	0.54	0.57	1.13	0.29	0.99	0.44	1.46
	min	0.11	0.10	0.11	3.4	0.24	0.99	0.38	1.6
	max	0.81	0.912	0.86	1.1	0.32	0.94	0.48	1.28

Table V. Model Performance comparison the *Concept Extraction* with the previous approach (CNN)

- The *Decision Tree* models have on average the best f1 score (0.17), precision (0.26), and recall (0.26) with the highest mean length (1.17). The *Random Forest* and *Logistic Regression* have performance of 0.13 (f1), precision of 0.20 and 0.22, and recall of 0.11. They differ in terms of the mean length with a score of 1.06 and 1.12. The *Naive Bayes* has a f1 score of 0.11, precision 0.16, recall 0.10, and a mean length of 1.14.
- The external feature measurements have an f1 score of 0.18 to 0.20, the precision of 0.25 to 0.28, recall of 0.15 to 0.17, and a mean length of 1.1 to 1.18. While the internal ones have a score of about 0.135 (f1), the precision of around 0.21, recall of 0.11, and a mean length of 1.12. Further, more *Logistic Regression* models have the best scores on the external feature measurements and *Decision Tree* models the best on the internal ones. Except the measurement *dec_tree_mean* where the *Naive Bayes* has the best performance.
- The number of samples has no overall impact on this evaluation. Only the *Naive Bayes* models have a higher f1 score with a higher amount of samples.
- Using the *full* features gives the best overall results compared to the *ngram* features with slightly worse results and the *transition* features.
- The Pearson correlation between the mean length with the f1 score and recall is 0.37, and with the precision 0.34.

The Table VII shows the models with the best performance on the *DUC* and *Hulth Dataset* of the trained models with regards to precision, recall, and f1 on the top five extracted *Keyphrase* per document. Additional they are compared with the previous approach, the EmbedRank d2v shown in [22], and the TextRank shown in [23].

Fig. 6. Keyphrase Extraction performance

Algorithm	DUC			Inspect/Hulth		
	pr	re	f1	pr	re	f1
Textual Feature precision	0.39	0.13	0.19	0.45	0.15	0.22
Textual Feature recall	0.21	0.30	0.25	0.30	0.37	0.33
Textual Feature f1	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.34	0.36	0.35
EmbedRank d2v [22]	0.31	0.20	0.24	0.42	0.26	0.32
TextRank	0.20	0.12	0.15	0.25	0.11	0.15
CNN [4]	0.31	0.17	0.23	0.44	0.17	0.25

Table VII. Comparison of the Keyphrase Extraction performance with the previous approach (CNN) and two others existing benchmarks

V-D. Model Interpretation

Methods of the model interpretation can help to understand the structure of the model. The Table IX shows the feature weight of the top 10 features based on the *total_n* measurement. Additional it contains an approximation of the feature importance of the four different model types trained on this feature set with 3 million samples. This approximation use 10 thousand samples and their prediction to approximate the feature importance for each of the four models (as introduced in [15]). Based on the approximation, the feature $rmsd_{\sigma_{\mu}}$ has a high importance and $chi_{seq_{\mu}}$ a low one for all models. Further more the feature idf_{μ} is important for tree based models and less for *Naive Bayes* or *Logistic Regression*.

Feature	Feature Weight	Importance Random Forest	Importance Decision Tree	Importance Logistic Regression	Importance Naive Bayes
$pmi_{all_{\mu}}$	0.45	0.06 (5)	0.07 (4)	0.15 (4)	0.05 (6)
$pmi_{seq_{\mu}}$	0.45	0.03 (8)	0.03 (7)	0.12 (5)	0.022 (9)
$rmsd_{\sigma_{\mu}}$	0.27	0.24 (2)	0.2 (3)	0.28 (1)	0.34 (1)
$tf_{rid}f_{\sigma_{\mu}}$	0.26	0.04 (7)	0.04 (6)	0.04 (6)	0.16 (3)
$z_{all_{\mu}}$	0.22	0.025 (9)	0.02 (9)	0.001 (10)	0.026 (7)
idf_{μ}	0.20	0.25 (1)	0.26 (2)	0.025 (8)	0.07 (5)
$chi_{seq_{\mu}}$	0.17	0.02 (10)	0.01 (10)	0.003 (9)	0.02 (10)
$pri_{\sigma_{\mu}}$	0.16	0.21 (3)	0.29 (1)	0.16 (3)	0.21 (2)
$pri_{\sigma_{\sigma}}$	0.14	0.05 (6)	0.024 (8)	0.19 (2)	0.08 (4)
$apmi_{all_{\mu}}$	0.13	0.08 (4)	0.069 (5)	0.034 (7)	0.03 (6)

Table IX. Comparison of the feature weighting and different blackbox feature importance

A more detailed way of analysing a single feature and the possible values of the features is calculating the partial dependence curve (as shown in [16]). It reveals the change of the prediction probability of class such as $p(\text{Concept})$ with regards to the different values of the feature. The Figure 7 shows this curve for the feature idf_{μ} . It shows that for a *Random Forest* model, the change of the idf_{μ} directly effects $p(\text{Concept})$ while for a *Logistic Regression* model it almost no impact.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the partial dependence curve of the feature idf_{μ} of the *N-Gram* for all the types of model

V-E. Decision Interpretation

The way of analyzing a single prediction (as in subsection II-E) enables the allows exploration of the effect of the single feature values. Table XIV shows the probability of being a *Concept* in the first row and the effect of a single feature value on the prediction in the other rows. A positive value increases the probability of being a *Concept*, and a negative score decreases this probability.

VI. DISCUSSION

According to seen results in section IV, the usage of the formulated features helps to produce understandable *Concept Extraction* models. Those models have a good performance with regards to generalizability, to the *Concept-Extraction* evaluation and the *Keyphrase Extraction* evaluation. A direct generalization measure is stated in subsection V-A. The Figure 3 reports high stability in terms of a low standard deviation of the precision of the different cross-validation runs. Two other indicators of the generalizability are the similar characteristic of the f1 score in Figure 3 and Figure 5 and performance differences of the four different test sets. The differences are smaller than expected, on average 3% precision and 2% recall.

Looking at the performance of the *Concept Extraction* evaluation (subsection V-B) reveals the best models are trained with features composed by the one of the external measurement and trained with a *Decision Tree*. Besides the high f1 scores, those models are trained with a smaller amount of time (compared to *Random Forest* models) and have a high correlation of precision and recall (as in Figure 4). Compared to the approach in [4], they have a better f1 score and precision performance.

The performance of *Keyphrase Extraction* (subsection V-C) shows that *Decision Tree* model - on average - outperform the other models again. The *Naive Bayes* has a surprisingly good performance, primarily when it uses just ten features or the feature measurement is *dec_tree_mean*. It seems like those models with a less strict *Concept* extraction (lower precision but higher recall score) can help to produce better results at the end of the pipeline. The less restrictive filtering can be one explanation so that the *Keyphrase* selection phase has a broader range of candidates to select and has thereby better possibilities. We already observed such behavior in previous research ([4]). Another interesting observation (based on Figure 6) is that model with a higher f1 score often have a lower mean length of the predicted *Concepts*. Especially the *Random Forest* models with high performance and a low mean length. The usage of a *Decision Tree* can reduce this downside. However, none of the best models can reach the mean length of the labeled *Concepts* (of about 1.5).

In general, the presented approach produce understandable and meaningful text features. They can encode a dynamic number of words within fixed dimensions. The features cover *N-Gram* itself, the neighbor words, and the transition into and out of it. This structure enables to take into account the surrounding context. The usage of internal and external measurements allows for producing limited sets of the best features without redundancies. Also, subsection V-D

and subsection V-E shows a way of understanding and analyzing the ongoing decision processed. This interpretability helps to comprehend the decision, increase the trust of the models, and understand the effect of the different values of a feature. Overall the models trained with the formulated features outperform the previous approach on the *Concept Extraction* and on the *Keyphrase Extraction*. A conclusive statement would require more experiments. The previous approach used another algorithm (Neural Network) in combination with a balanced set of features (50% *Concepts* and 50% *Non-Concepts*) to build the models.

VII. CONCLUSION

The good performance of the trained *Concept Extraction* models with the features of the presented *Textual Feature Framework* shows the meaningfulness of those features. Different to word embeddings, those features are human-understandable and interpretable. They can help to comprehend the produced prediction of for single sample and to get additional insights of a dataset.

VIII. OUTLOOK

Based on the findings of this paper, there are three follow up aspect to reason about. First of all, get a better comparison between the Neural Network based approach and the presented one by doing more experiments (as mentioned in section VI). Second, the evaluation of the *Textual Feature Framework* on a different task such as a multi-label classification, or regression. Moreover, in the end, using the present features in Recurrent Neural Networks (such as LSTM) or Attention-based models (such as Transformer Networks). Those methods have the advantage that the context is encoded implicitly by construction.

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APPENDIX

A. Feature Formulation

Symbol	Description	Cat.
idf_{σ}	The <i>statistic</i> of the Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	N
idf_{μ}	The <i>statistic</i> of the Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$ridf_{\sigma}$	The <i>statistic</i> of the Residual Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$ridf_{\mu}$	The <i>statistic</i> of the Residual Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$rmsd_{\sigma\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the Relative Maximum Spread Distances of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$rmsd_{\mu\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the Relative Maximum Spread Distances of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$rmsd_{\sigma\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the Relative Maximum Spread Distances of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$rmsd_{\mu\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the Relative Maximum Spread Distances of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$tf_{\sigma\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$tf_{\mu\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$tf_{\sigma\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$tf_{\mu\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$tfidf_{\sigma\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the multiplication of Term Frequency and Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$tfidf_{\mu\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the multiplication of Term Frequency and Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$tfidf_{\sigma\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the multiplication of Term Frequency and Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$tfidf_{\mu\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the multiplication of Term Frequency and Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$tfridf_{\sigma\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the multiplication of Term Frequency and Residual Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$tfridf_{\mu\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the multiplication of Term Frequency and Residual Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$tfridf_{\sigma\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the multiplication of Term Frequency and Residual Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$tfridf_{\mu\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the multiplication of Term Frequency and Residual Inverse Term Frequency of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$pr_{\sigma\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the occurrence of all the prior words of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$pr_{\mu\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the occurrence of all the prior words of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$pr_{\sigma\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the occurrence of all the prior words of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$pr_{\mu\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the occurrence of all the prior words of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$po_{\sigma\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the occurrence of all the posterior words of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$po_{\mu\sigma}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the occurrence of all the posterior words of each word w in a N -Gram	S
$po_{\sigma\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the occurrence of all the posterior words of each word w in a N -Gram	N
$po_{\mu\mu}$	The <i>compound statistic</i> of the <i>statistic</i> of the occurrence of all the posterior words of each word w in a N -Gram	S

Table X. Frequency Based Feature Extraction

Symbol	Description	Cat.
p	The probability of the sample defined as $P(s_1) * P(s_2 s_1) * \dots * P(s_n s_{n-1})$	N S
p_{σ} p_{μ}	The <i>statistic</i> of the probability of each stem of the sample	N S
$p_{seq\sigma}$ $p_{seq\mu}$ $p_{all\sigma}$ $p_{all\mu}$	The <i>statistic</i> of the conditional probability of all sequential stem pairs and all combinations of stem pairs	N S
pmi	The pointwise mutual information for stem pair s_a, s_b , defined as $\log\left(\frac{P(s_a, s_b)}{P(s_a) * P(s_b)}\right)$	T
$pmi_{seq\sigma}$ $pmi_{seq\mu}$ $pmi_{all\sigma}$ $pmi_{all\mu}$	The <i>statistic</i> of the pointwise mutual information of all sequential stem pairs and all combinations of stem pairs.	N S
$apmi$	The average pointwise mutual information for stem pair s_a, s_b , defined as $\log\left(\frac{P(s_a, s_b)}{P(s_a) * P(s_b)}\right)$ $+ \log\left(\frac{P(\neg s_a, s_b)}{P(\neg s_a) * P(s_b)}\right)$ $+ \log\left(\frac{P(s_a, \neg s_b)}{P(s_a) * P(\neg s_b)}\right)$ $+ \log\left(\frac{P(\neg s_a, \neg s_b)}{P(\neg s_a) * P(\neg s_b)}\right)$	T
$apmi_{seq\sigma}$ $apmi_{seq\mu}$ $apmi_{all\sigma}$ $apmi_{all\mu}$	The <i>statistic</i> of the average pointwise mutual information of all sequential stem pairs and all combinations of stem pairs.	N S
lr	The likelihood ratio of the conditional probability of the occurrence the stems s_b given s_b and the conditional probability of stem (s_b) given any other stem s_b , defined as $\frac{P(s_a, s_b)}{P(\neg s_a, s_b)}$	T

Symbol	Description	Cat.
$lr_{seq\sigma}$ $lr_{seq\mu}$ $lr_{all\sigma}$ $lr_{all\mu}$	The <i>statistic</i> of the likelihood ratio of all sequential stem pairs and all combinations of stem pairs.	N S
or	The odds ratio ([1]) of the pair of stems s_a, s_b measures the strength of association of the existence and inexistence of s_a and s_b , defined as $\frac{P(s_a, s_b) * P(\neg s_a, \neg s_b)}{P(\neg s_a, s_b) * P(s_a, \neg s_b)}$	T
$or_{seq\sigma}$ $or_{seq\mu}$ $or_{all\sigma}$ $or_{all\mu}$	The <i>statistic</i> of the average point-wise mutual information of all sequential stem pairs and all combinations of stem pairs.	N S
t	The t-score for a stem pair s_a, s_b , defined as $\frac{P(s_a, s_b) - P(s_a) * P(s_b)}{\sqrt{P(s_a, s_b)}}$ [24] proposed the t-score as a measurement of the randomness of the association of the stems.	T
$t_{seq\sigma}$ $t_{seq\mu}$ $t_{all\sigma}$ $t_{all\mu}$	The <i>statistic</i> of the t-score of all sequential stem pairs and all combinations of stem pairs.	N S
z	The z-score for a stem pair s_a, s_b (as shown in [24]) acts as a another indicator for the pair of stems It gives a higher value to significant stem pairs and is defined as: $\frac{P(s_a, s_b) - P(s_a) * P(s_b)}{\sqrt{P(s_a) * P(s_b)}}$	T
$z_{seq\sigma}$ $z_{seq\mu}$ $z_{all\sigma}$ $z_{all\mu}$	The <i>statistic</i> of the z-score of all sequential stem pairs and all combinations of stem pairs.	N S
chi	The chi score for a stem pair s_a, s_b , as $\frac{x^2}{y}$ where x and y are defines as: $x = P(s_a, s_b) * P(\neg s_a, \neg s_b) - P(\neg s_a, s_b) * P(s_a, \neg s_b)$ $y = (P(s_a, s_b) + P(s_a, \neg s_b)) * (P(s_a, s_b) + P(\neg s_a, s_b)) * (P(\neg s_a, \neg s_b) + P(s_a, \neg s_b)) * (P(\neg s_a, \neg s_b) + P(\neg s_a, s_b))$ This formulation is based on the chi quadratic test (shown in [25]) and measures the independence of the existence and in existence of s_a and s_b .	T

Symbol	Description	Cat.
$chi_{seq\sigma}$ $chi_{seq\mu}$ $chi_{all\sigma}$ $chi_{all\mu}$	The <i>statistic</i> of the chi-score of all sequential stem pairs and all combinations of stem pairs.	N S

Table XI. Probabilistic Based Feature Extraction

Symbol	Description	Cat.
cos_{tfidf} cos_{tfridf} cos_{po}	The cosine similarity of a pair of stems based on the three matrices $TFIDF_{SVD}$, $TFRIDF_{SVD}$ and $TFIDF_{PO}$	T
$cos_{tfidf_{seq\sigma}}$ $cos_{tfidf_{seq\mu}}$ $cos_{tfridf_{seq\sigma}}$ $cos_{tfridf_{seq\mu}}$ $cos_{po_{seq\sigma}}$ $cos_{po_{seq\mu}}$ $cos_{tfidf_{all\sigma}}$ $cos_{tfidf_{all\mu}}$ $cos_{tfridf_{all\sigma}}$ $cos_{tfridf_{all\mu}}$ $cos_{po_{all\sigma}}$ $cos_{po_{all\mu}}$	The statistic of the cosine similarity of all sequential stem pairs and all combinations of stem pairs based on all of the three matrices.	T
euc_{tfidf} euc_{tfridf} euc_{po}	The euclidean similarity of a pair of stems in all of the three spaces	T
$euc_{tfidf_{seq\sigma}}$ $euc_{tfidf_{seq\mu}}$ $euc_{tfridf_{seq\sigma}}$ $euc_{tfridf_{seq\mu}}$ $euc_{po_{seq\sigma}}$ $euc_{po_{seq\mu}}$ $euc_{tfidf_{all\sigma}}$ $euc_{tfidf_{all\mu}}$ $euc_{tfridf_{all\sigma}}$ $euc_{tfridf_{all\mu}}$ $euc_{po_{all\sigma}}$ $euc_{po_{all\mu}}$	The statistic of the cosine similarity of all sequential stem pairs and all combinations of stem pairs based on all of the three matrices.	T

Table XII. Similarity Based Feature Extraction

	Random Forest	Decision Tree	Logistic Regression	Naive Bayes
Concept probability	78.5%	100%	41.1%	99%
$pmi_{all\mu}$	0.056	0.1349	0.0678	0.042
$pmi_{seq\mu}$	0.016	-0.0021	-0.038	0.0328
$rmsd_{\sigma\mu}$	0.0089	0.033	-0.057	-0.0167
$tfridf_{\sigma\sigma}$	-0.03	-0.028	-0.036	-0.0178
$z_{all\mu}$	0.0013	0.0054	0.0014	0.011
idf_{μ}	0.018	0.056	0.0073	0.012
$chi_{seq\mu}$	-0.015	0.0015	0.0099	-0.005
$pri_{\sigma\mu}$	-0.0176	-0.0384	-0.0537	-0.0089
$pri_{\sigma\sigma}$	-0.0249	-0.0388	0.078	-0.0079
$apmi_{all\mu}$	-0.065	-0.16	-0.078	-0.0027

Table XIV. Comparison of the local analysis of the classification probability for the N -Gram Western Hemisphere with the predecessor *the* and successor $\langle SE \rangle$ as a Concept